

Study of placenta previa and its maternal and fetal outcomes in a tertiary care hospital in Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

Background: Placenta previa is one of the most important complications during pregnancy which is associated with various complications in the mother and the newborn. Identifying the factors associated with it would help in predicting its occurrence and also associated complications so that morbidity and mortality could be minimized.

Objectives: To study the incidence, characteristics and outcome of placenta previa and its maternal and fetal outcomes.

Methods:

A prospective observational study was conducted between June 2020 and June 2021 at a tertiary care hospital in South India among 50 pregnant women with features suggestive of placenta previa (PP) such as bright red vaginal bleeding without pain during the second half of pregnancy along with uterine contraction and abdominal pain. Detailed medical history was collected and physical examination, abdominal and transvaginal ultrasonogram were done. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethics committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all study participants. The data was analysed using SPSS software and p value less than 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results: The incidence of placenta previa was 0.42%. Mean age of the antenatal women with PP was 24.9 years and the mean gestational age at diagnosis was 32.3 weeks. A total of 66% had history of previous LSCS which was the most common risk factor identified. Previous curettage was done in 12%. LSCS was the mode of delivery in 98% of the women. Most

common complication present among the patients was atonic PPH (54%). Placenta accreta syndrome was present in 16%. Neonatal death happened in 12% and still birth rate was 4%. Mean APGAR score was 5.3 and 6.6 at 1 minute and 5 minutes respectively. Among the total number of 50 deliveries, 68% of the neonates had low birth weight. Prematurity was the most common complication (62%) followed by neonatal jaundice (26%) and respiratory distress (12%).

Conclusion: Placenta previa is found to be associated with previous LSCS which was the most common risk factor. Neonatal death, still birth and respiratory distress were high among neonates born between 28 to 32 weeks of gestation.

Key words: placenta previa, risk factors, complications, incidence, outcome

Introduction

Normal implantation is very crucial for successful pregnancy and positive outcome. When there is abnormality in implantation of placenta it leads to various abnormal entities viz., placental shape abnormality, maternal vascular malperfusion, velamentous cord insertion, abnormal placental location and morbidly adherent placenta. Placenta previa (PP) is one of the disorders during antenatal period which denotes location of placenta within 2cm of internal os. It may present as complete/partial covering of internal cervical os with placenta and is associated with multiple maternal and neonatal complications.¹

Globally, the incidence of placenta previa ranges between 0.5% to 1% of pregnancies.²

The incidence rate of placenta previa is higher during mid pregnancy than the later weeks such as after 36 weeks of pregnancy which could possibly be explained with formation of lower segment of uterus in later weeks and trophotropism which results in resolution of placenta previa.³ The factors such as increasing maternal age, increase in rate of cesarean section deliveries, increase in use of assisted reproductive technology The risk factors of placenta

previa reported in previous literatures include age of the mother, parity, previous caesarean section and history of placenta previa, treatment for infertility, smoking during pregnancy and recurrent abortion.⁴

Placenta previa is associated with increase in rate of cesarean section deliveries, severe morbid adherence of placenta with the uterine wall, postpartum hemorrhage and resulting anemia and increase in rate of hysterectomy in the peripartum period.^{5,6,7,8} Invasive placentation such as placenta accreta, increta and percreta increases the risk of mortality.

Placenta previa is also associated with various perinatal complications which includes low birth weight, preterm birth, neonatal anemia, birth asphyxia and birth of child with congenital anomalies. Placenta previa increases the probability of risk of perinatal mortality.²

Since placenta previa is associated with multiple maternal and perinatal complications, assessment of the factors associated with placenta previa and its complications is necessary to improve the outcomes by incorporating the assessment of these factors and early management in clinical practice.

Materials and methods

Study design: Observational study using cross sectional study design.

Study area: The study was conducted in the department of obstetrics and gynecology at a medical college hospital in Tamil Nadu, India.

Study duration: The study was conducted for a period of 1 year from June 2020 to June 2021.

Study population: Pregnant women presented with features suggestive of placenta previa during the study period.

Sample size =50 pregnant women with placenta previa.

Sampling technique: Convenient sampling method was followed to select the pregnant women participated in the study.

Inclusion criteria: Patients presented with the main symptom of bright red vaginal bleeding without pain during the second half of pregnancy along with uterine contraction and abdominal pain.

Exclusion criteria

Intra Uterine Fetal Development (IUID) <24 weeks

Pre-eclampsia

Twin pregnancy

Premature birth of other cause

Study investigations to diagnose placenta previa

1. Abdominal ultra sound
2. Trans vaginal ultra sound which is done by wandlike device placed inside the vagina.

Study procedure:

Pregnant women who presented with vaginal bleeding and admitted during the study period were studied and the data were analysed.

Data based on age, number of pregnancies and history of previous pregnancies were noted.

Detailed medical history, physical examination, abdominal USG and transvaginal USG were also collected.

Ethical approval: Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the institutional ethics committee of Chengalpattu Medical College, Chengalpattu. Written informed consent was obtained from all the study participants.

Statistical analysis: The collected data was entered in Microsoft Excel and transferred to SPSS software for analysis. Descriptive statistical analysis for performed initially. To identify the association between the variables chi-square test was used. For all tests of statistical significance, p value of <0.05 was taken as significant.

Results

The study included a total of 50 antenatal women with placenta previa. The mean age of the women was 24.9 ± 3.8 years which was ranging from 18 to 33 years. Most of the women were aged between 18 to 23 years (40%) and 24 to 28 years (40%). The gestational age was 29 to 32 weeks among 23 (46%) women and 33 to 37 years among 27 (54%) women. The median gestational age was 33 weeks. Parity was 2 among 50% of the women. The mean hemoglobin level was 9.26 ± 0.98 gm/dl which was ranging from 7 to 12gm%. The details are described in table 1.

The most common risk factor found among the women participated in the study was previous LSCS (66%) followed by previous curettage (12%) which is described in table 2.

Among the 50 pregnancies, 42 (84%) resulted in low birth weight. There were 6 neonatal deaths (12%) and 2 stillbirths (4%). Forty three children (86%) had APGAR score of ≤ 7 at 1 minute. Of the 50 births, 68% were low birth weight and 62% were premature birth. The other outcomes of pregnancy are described in table 3.

The maternal complications associated with placenta previa are given in bar chart 1 with atonic postpartum hemorrhage as most common complication. Among the 50 women 48 (96%) required blood transfusion.

The factors associated with maternal outcomes such as postpartum hemorrhage, hemorrhagic shock, placenta accreta syndrome were analysed with which it showed that parity had significant association with significantly less proportion of women in low parity having

complications compared to their counterparts. Higher proportion of women with anemia had complications, yet this association was not statistically significant. (Table 4)

Among various factors analysed, gestational age had significant association with neonatal outcomes with neonates in the gestational age of 28 to 32 weeks having complications such as neonatal death and still birth. (Table 5).

Discussion

The present cross sectional study has included 50 women with placenta previa and analysed the factors associated with it and the maternal and neonatal outcomes. The mean age of the women with PP in the present study was 24.9 years. This is lower compared to the studies by Kothapalli et (28.6 yrs); Prasanth et al (27.4 yrs) and Gargari et al (29.8).^{9,10,11} The most common age group who presented with PP in our study was 24 to 28 years (48%). A study by Prasanth et al reported PP to be common in the age group of 20 to 29 years which was 72.9%.¹⁰ Similarly, another study by Devarmani et al also reported most common age group with PP as 20 to 29 years (35%).¹² A study from Ethiopian population also reported similar finding with nearly 70% of women with PP being less than 30 years of age.¹³ In our study we found half of the study group were in parity two. Similar to the present study another study done in India by Kothapalli et al, Prasanth et al and Devarmani et al also reported high proportion of women presenting with placenta previa were multiparous.^{9,10,12} In contrast to these study reports, a study by Adere et al reported equal proportion of women those who were nulliparous/primiparous and multiparous presented with PP.¹³ Another study by Gargari et al also reported lower proportion of multiparous women with PP which was 19.3%.¹¹ In the current study more than 50% were in the gestational age of 33 to 37 weeks which is similar to other studies by Kothapalli et al and Devarmani et al who also reported such finding.^{9,12} A study done by Adere et al reported that 20% of women presented with PP in the gestational age

of 34 to 36 weeks and almost 50% presented after 37 weeks.¹³ The incidence of placenta previa is increasing worldwide due to the increase in incidence of cesarean section deliveries which is one of the most important factors. The reason for occurrence of placenta previa with previous cesarean section is due to presence of uterine scar in the lower segment of uterus leading to implantation of placenta in the lower uterine segment. The present study results are also similar to this global trend with major proportion of women in this study with history of previous caesarean section. Previous other studies by Kothapalli et al, Gargari et al, Wasim et al, Sidhiq et al have also reported similar findings.^{9,11,14,15} Anemia was present among 92% of women in the present study. This is little higher than the results of another study by Devarmani et al who stated that 84% had anemia.¹² Adere et al reported anemia among 31% of women with PP.¹³ Atonic PPH was the most common complication (54%) among mothers as per the results of the present study. This is in line with the results of two other studies who also reported postpartum hemorrhage as the most common complication among 78.2% and 12.2%.^{9,15} In the present study blood transfusion was needed for 96% of women. This proportion is higher compared to other studies by Prasanth et al in India (39.6%), Gargari et al (11.9%), Adere et al (40%), Sidhiq et al (57.4%).^{10,11,13,15} This difference could be because of difference in the clinical presentation while reaching the health facility and type of placenta previa. The most common neonatal complication reported in a study by Kothapalli et al was preterm birth (6%).⁹ The proportion of neonatal death was 12% in the present study. This is higher than the results of other studies by Wasim et al (4.6%) and Sidhiq et al (6.5%).^{14,15} Another study by Devarmani et al reported higher proportion of perinatal deaths (28%).¹² Respiratory distress syndrome was one of the most important neonatal complications reported in few other studies which ranges from Gargari et al 30.9%. In the current study RDS was found among 12% of the neonates.¹¹

Conclusion

Placenta previa is one of the most important complication during pregnancy which is common among multiparous women and in those with history of previous caesarean section. Previous curettage is also one of the risk factors but only next to caesarean section. PP is associated with higher incidence of postpartum hemorrhage resulting in shock and the need for blood transfusion. PP also results in higher proportion of preterm birth and neonatal mortality.

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Table 1: Description of the study participants with placenta previa (N = 50)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
<20	2	4.0%
20 to 24	24	48.0%
25 to 29	17	34.0%
≥30	7	14.0%
Gestational age (weeks)		
29 to 32 weeks	23	46.0
33 to 37 weeks	27	54.0
Parity		
0	9	18.0
1	16	32.0
2	25	50.0
Fetal heart rate		
Fetal distress	14	28.0
Normal fetal heart rate	36	72.0
Hemoglobin level		
Anemia	46	92.0
Normal	4	8.0

Table 2: Risk factors for placenta previa

Risk factors	Frequency	Percent
Multi fetal Gestation	3	6.0
Preeclampsia, Eclampsia	3	6.0
Previous curettage	6	12.0
Previous LSCS	33	66.0
Unknown	5	10.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 3: Outcome of pregnancy associated with placenta previa

Variable	Number of neonates	Percentage
Low birth weight	34	68.0
APGAR score		
At 1 minute ≤ 7	43	86.0
At 5 minute ≤ 7	32	64.0
Neonatal death	6	12.0
Still birth	2	4.0
Live birth	42	84.0
Neonatal jaundice	13	26.0
Prematurity	31	62.0
Respiratory distress	6	12.0

Bar chart 1: Complications of placenta previa among mothers

Table 4: Factors associated with maternal outcome

Factors	PPH/Hemorrhagic shock	PAS	No complications	Total	p value
Age of the mother					
<20 years	1 (12.5%)	1 (2.8%)	0	2 (4%)	0.49
20 to 24 years	18 (50%)	4 (50%)	2 (33.3%)	24 (48%)	
25 to 29 years	11 (30.6%)	2 (25%)	4 (66.7%)	17 (34%)	
≥30 years	6 (16.7%)	1 (12.5%)	0	7 (14%)	
Parity					
0	9 (25%)	0	0	9 (18%)	0.015*
1	14 (38.9%)	0	2 (33.3%)	16 (32%)	
2	13 (36.1%)	8 (100%)	4 (66.7%)	25 (50%)	
Gestational age					
28 to 32 weeks	16 (44.4%)	4 (50%)	3 (50%)	23 (46%)	0.93
33 to 37 weeks	20 (55.6%)	4 (50%)	3 (50%)	27 (54%)	
Anemia					
Anemic	32 (88.9%)	8 (100%)	6 (100%)	46 (92%)	0.42
No anemia	4 (11.1%)	0	0	4 (8%)	

*p value Significant

Table 5: Factors associated with neonatal outcome

Factors	Perinatal outcome			Total	p value
	Live Birth	Neonatal Death	Still Birth		
Age of the mother					
<20 years	1 (2.4%)	1 (16.7%)	0	2 (4%)	0.38
20 to 24 years	22 (52.4%)	2 (33.3%)	0	24 (48%)	
25 to 29 years	14 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (50%)	17 (34%)	
≥30 years	5 (11.9%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (50%)	7 (14%)	
Parity					
0	7 (16.7%)	2 (33.3%)	0	9 (18%)	0.52
1	14 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0	16 (32%)	
2	21 (50%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (100%)	25 (50%)	
Anemia					
Anemic	39 (92.9%)	5 (83.3%)	2 (100%)	46 (92%)	0.66
No anemia	3 (7.1%)	1 (16.7%)	0	4 (8%)	
Gestational age					
28 to 32 weeks	15 (35.7%)	6 (100%)	2 (100%)	23 (46%)	0.004*
33 to 37 weeks	27 (64.3%)	0	0	27 (54%)	

*p value Significant